

Original Article

Death Anxiety, Coping Strategies, and Insomnia in Patients with Chronic Illness

Akhtar Parveen¹, Dr. Shagufta Bibi², & Dr. Muhammad Luqman Khan³¹ M.Phil. Scholar, Department of Psychology, Riphah International University, Faisalabad Campus, Punjab, Pakistan.² Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, Riphah International University, Faisalabad Campus, Punjab, Pakistan.³ Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, Riphah International University, Faisalabad Campus, Punjab, Pakistan.**JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS****Copyright** © The Author(s). 2025

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribute 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author(s) and source are credited.

How to Cite:

Parveen, A., Bibi, S., & Khan, M. L. (2025). Death Anxiety, Coping Strategies, and Insomnia in Patients with Chronic Illness. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(2), 1-10.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15712501>

Abstract

The mediating function of coping mechanisms in the connection between sleeplessness and death fear is examined in this study. The findings indicate a strong positive relationship between sleeplessness and death anxiety. The cross-sectional survey research approach served as the groundwork for this investigation. A sample of patients (N= 250) with chronic illness will participate in this present study. This study uses the Insomnia Severity Index, Death Anxiety Inventory, and Brief Cope Scale. Information was gathered from the Faisalabad division's hospitals. The technique of purposeful sampling was employed to gather data. Prior to distributing the surveys, the participants gave their informed consent. Results of present study can help patients to maximize their ability to cope with this disease and also help professionals and psychologist for resolution the issues in the better way and make special strategies to maximize their capability to cope with problematic situation and try to minimize negative thoughts, feelings

Keywords: Coping Strategies, Death Anxiety and Insomnia

Introduction

The American Psychiatric Association (2013) states in the DSM-5 that symptoms of insomnia disorder are trouble falling or staying asleep. An appropriate diagnosis requires a detailed assessment of sleep habits, daytime functioning, and underlying physiological and psychological variables. Chronic sleeplessness is lead to cardiac illness, anxiety, depression and cognitive decline. According to epidemiological research conducted thus far, the disorder's reported prevalence varies between 10% and 34%. Subjective complaints of insomnia have been linked in multiple studies to an increased risk of coronary events in the future. There is a correlation between coronary artery disease (CAD) and insomnia, according to recent prospective surveys. Sleeplessness has been linked to a number of medical, psychiatric, and psychosocial conditions, according to crosssectional epidemiological studies. Additionally, hypertension has been shown to be one of the only factors linked to insomnia (Matsuda et al., 2022).

Several prospective studies have shown that patients with a non-dipping blood pressure (BP) profile are more likely to experience cardiac problems than those with a decreasing BP profile. Sleep disturbances and blood pressure combined effects on cardiovascular health (Khoso, et al., 2024; Sultana & Imran, 2024; Ahmad, Bibi & Imran, 2023). Understanding these connections could lead to more effective management strategies for patients suffering from hypertension. Purpose of this study is which clinical and biological structures and sleeplessness in hypertension patients. (Forshaw et al., 2022).

Whether the issue is trouble falling or staying asleep, common awakenings with trouble falling back to sleep, or non-restorative sleep, insomnia has a significant and negative influence on health. It is commonly comorbid, and it is difficult to cure. More than 50% of adults suffer from insomnia on occasion, and 10% to 15% do soon a regular basis. Because of its harmful impact on place of work presentism / absenteeism , accident risk, and

* **Corresponding Author:** Dr. Muhammad Luqman Khan | Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, Riphah International University, Faisalabad Campus, Punjab, Pakistan.

✉ luqman.khan0078@gmail.com

© 2025 | College of Education, Swabi, Pakistan.

healthcare consumption. Since human psychophysiology deals with the interaction between the mind and body and psychological factors (Rosler et al., 2024).

The concept of death has long been a profound and influential aspect of human existence, often serving as a central theme in artistic expression and philosophical thought. The term death anxiety refers to the unease or fear that arises from an individual's awareness of their own mortality (Abdel-Khalek, 2005).

The distress and worry associated with expecting and being aware of dying, death. It usually consists of emotional, cognitive, and motivational elements that change depending on an individual's developing life involvements (Khan, Haq, & Naseer, 2022; Shaukat, Rehman, & ul Haq, 2021). Death anxiety at different ages might be influenced by cultural differences in how people conceptualize death. Numerous studies have demonstrated that death anxiety is present in many civilizations, including Iranian culture (Pandya & Kathuria, 2021).

Despite the fact that everyone will eventually die, the uncertainty surrounding death can generate anxiety (Shaukat, et al., 2020; ul Haq & ur Rehman, 2017). Individuals who receive a diagnosis of an incurable illness are confronted with death. Anxiety and tension can arise when a fatal condition, like cancer, is diagnosed. In 2018, cancer was the second most common cause of death worldwide (WHO, 2020). Cancer has impacted millions of people worldwide, and scientists predict that 11.4 million individuals will be impacted by the disease by 2020. According to estimates, one in three persons will have cancer at some point in their lives (Ferlay et al., 2014).

The fear and worry associated with anticipating and being aware of dying, death, and nonexistence is known as death anxiety. According to Lehto and Stein (2009), it usually consists of emotional, cognitive, and motivational elements that change life experiences. Death-related anxiety is a complicated idea. It was described, along with its different presentations. Death anxiety encompasses fear and more, might affect death anxiety (Jaleel, & Sarmad, 2024; Jalil, Sarmad, & Shafi, 2023; Muhammad, et al., 2020). Developmental psychology claims that aging is a stage associated with a variety of health problems, the loss of a loved one, and deteriorating cognitive abilities. Seniors may experience terror or death dread as their lives come to an end (Amjad, 2014).

The knowledge that everyone will eventually die can be extremely frightening and unsettling. Coping strategies for death are different and unique to each individual (Danish, Akhtar & Imran, 2025; Mankash, et al., 2025; Hafeez, Yaseen & Imran, 2019). The majority of individuals worry about death to some extent because it is impossible to foretell with precision. One of the most frequently mentioned psychological issues among patients with terminal illnesses, including cancer, is anxiety. As a result, research on death fear has significant ramifications for cancer therapy and care. Cancer patients' degree of death dread is influenced by social, cultural, and personal factors (Peters et al., 2013).

The coping styles of positive and negative coping are very different. People who frequently choose a positive coping style do not view possibilities, demands, and dangers as possible threats, harms, or losses. Instead, they view difficult circumstances as personal obstacles. Positive coping in the workplace can result in positive feelings and actions that promote communicative well-being, professional and personal growth, and more individualized experiences and resources that boost competency (Cheney et al., 2008).

Coping techniques specifically designed to manage stress are included in the task-oriented coping dimension (e.g., mental imagery, effort expenditure, and relaxation). For instance, two cross-sectional studies conducted nationwide in Japan have demonstrated an inverse relationship between insomnia symptoms and adaptive coping methods (Iqbal, Shah & Abid, 2025; Ivascu, et al., 2022; Ghulam, et al., 2019). Distraction-oriented coping techniques, such as distancing and mental distraction, focus attention on irrelevant elements of the sporting event. Athletes can use disengagement-oriented coping mechanisms, such as emotional venting and withdrawal, to distance themselves from efforts to pursue their own objectives (Kayani, et al., 2023; Khan, et al., 2021; Naseer, et al., 2021; Khan & Khan, 2020). Buy Customers who employ problem-oriented coping actively look for constructive ways to manage their anxiety and alter the situation that causes it (Baillette et al., 2021).

Positive evaluations are traits of positive coping. Palliative coping and more emotionfocused coping are used to differentiate bad coping. Negative coping style users frequently have distorted thought patterns, negative assessments, and inaccurate self-evaluations. They try to avoid stressful events and decrease distress by concentrating on negative ideas. "Continually shifting cognitive and behavioral efforts to manage specific external and internal demands that are appraised as taxing or exceeding the resources of the person" (Bigges et al., 2017).

It has been determined that coping mechanisms contribute to sleep disorders, such as insomnia. In individuals with arterial hypertension, the relationship between coping mechanisms, perceived stress, and sleeplessness symptoms may be modulated by psychological factors. For instance, maladaptive coping mechanisms like "giving up on problem-solving" and "enduring problems patiently" were found to be strongly correlated with insomnia symptoms in a nationwide cross-sectional study conducted in Japan (Cheng et al., 2016).

Literature Review

This literature aims to separate the "facts" of death fear that have been reasonably well established from the abundance of reports. Philosophers, sociologists, doctors, nurses, psychologists, anthropologists, attorneys, educators, theologians, political scientists, and art historians have all contributed to thanatology since its inception (Shah, Qazi & Khan, 2025; Naseer, Rehan & Shah, 2024; Malik, Hanif & Elahi, 2025). Psychologists have mostly studied death anxiety, with sporadic input from other social scientists and health care providers. In the 1980s, interest in death anxiety research peaked, then experienced another growing spurt before finally declining.

Despite how strong these arguments may be, there is no philosophical or practical justification for drawing a boundary between fear and anxiety. The psychoanalytic camp, which associates anxiety with the manifestation of unconscious tensions, has historically provided the best theoretical support for the distinction (Neimeyer et al., 2018).

This article uses evolutionary approach of concept analysis to identify the distinguishing characteristics, antecedents, and repercussions of the notion of death anxiety. A comprehensive assessment of the literature on death anxiety covering the years 1980–2007 was conducted. The articles were classified and summarized. Defined characteristics (emotion, cognitive, experiential, developmental, sociocultural shaping, and source of motivation), antecedents (unpredictable situations and stressful environments, diagnosis of a life-threatening illness or event, and experiences with death and dying), and consequences (adaptive and maladaptive presentations) were the outcomes of inductive data analyses (Regier, 2013).

The findings are significant since there is a dearth of comprehensive research on death anxiety in the nursing literature 49 published and unpublished research articles about the association between death anxiety and older adults' age, ego integrity, gender, institutionalization, medical and psychological issues and religiosity were quantitatively summarized in this review of the literature (Sohail-Rehan, & Ul-Haq, 2018; Haq, 2017; ul Haq, 2012). The findings showed that higher levels of death anxiety in older adults are predicted by lower ego integrity, more physical issues, and more psychological issues. For the predictor institutionalization, a link was discovered that was suggestive yet ambiguous (Jaleel, Rabbani, & Sarmad, 2025; Ali, et al., 2020; Ahmad, 2018).

The review also quantitatively illustrated the significance of sampling from the senior population and employing reliable techniques to measure death dread. As they say, we may learn by looking backwards, but we can also learn by looking forward (Azhar, 2024; Azhar & Imran, 2024; Azhar, et al., 2022). A person's beliefs, aspirations, and anxieties regarding the nature and significance of death may have a greater impact on his or her thoughts and actions than we realize (Khan & Haq, 2025; Haq & Khan, 2024). The goal of this systematic review and meta-analysis was to summarize the results of different approaches to reducing fear and anxiety related to dying. The databases Science Direct, Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, Cochrane Library, and CHINAL were searched for studies published between January 2010 and June 2022.

Chronic disease patients frequently experience death anxiety. A new theoretical framework called "death literacy" helps patients understand death better, talk about it, and accept it as a normal part of life. Comparing patients' and caregivers' degrees of death dread was another goal. After evaluating the included papers' methodological quality, a meta-analysis was carried out utilizing the DerSimonian–Laird technique to examine variations in death fear between patients and caregivers and Hedges' g as the impact size index, the results of the studies indicated moderate levels of death anxiety in caregivers (Lehto & Stein, 2009).

Sleeplessness was positively correlated with anxiety and sadness according to logistic regression analysis. Up to 10% of people in Western industrialized nations suffers from chronic insomnia. It is typified by awakenings, or the sensation that sleep is not restorative, together with notable emotional, social, or professional deficits during the day. Cognitive behavioral interventions (CBT-I) and hypnotic therapy with benzodiazepine receptor agonists and sedative antidepressants are the mainstays of current therapeutic approaches. Despite the well-established

efficacy of these medicines, a significant percentage of patients either show no improvement or are resistant to treatment (Wolinska et al., 2020).

At least in Europe, the issue of long-term medication treatment for chronic insomnia remains unsolved and requires immediate attention. In order to develop new, logical treatment options, integrated neuro-scientific methods must provide hints about the mechanisms and (Parveen, et al., 2020; ul haq, 2019; Ali & Haq 2017). We'll evaluate and critically discuss the key challenges surrounding the treatment of insomnia in the future, particularly in Europe (Al Maqbali, 2023).

Patients with chronic illnesses, such as chronic heart failure (CHF), frequently have insomnia, which is a major cause of exhaustion and a low quality of life. Because nocturnal symptoms like cough, orthopnea, paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea, and nocturia impair sleep, the path physiology of CHF frequently results in weariness. Hypoxemia or insufficient perfusion of the brain, skeletal muscle, or visceral bodily organs can be caused by inadequate heart function. This can lead to organ failure or dysfunction and could exacerbate fatigue. Sleep disruptions are linked to a higher incidence of comorbidities, such as depression, and have a detrimental impact on many aspects of quality of life. This page discusses treatment choices, sleep disruptions caused by cardiac medications, and insomnia in people with congestive heart failure (CHF) (Riemann et al., 2010).

Insomnia is characterized by trouble falling asleep, along with some kind of impairment during the day. In the current review, we give an overview of recent studies on the relationship between insomnia and cardiovascular disease (Naseer, et al., 2024; Shah et al., 2023; Aurangzeb, & Haq, 2012). We can infer that, independent of traditional coronary risk factors, there is mounting evidence that sleeplessness is linked to an elevated risk for cardiovascular disease. Additionally, hypertension and an increased resting heart rate both of which are known to contribute to cardiovascular disease are probably linked to insomnia. But the evidence that is now available is not entirely consistent, and the majority of the findings have not been conclusively repeated.

The most common sleep condition in the US is insomnia, which is highly associated with several cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). Several observational studies conducted over the last ten years have shown a correlation between sleeplessness and incident cardiovascular disease (CVD) morbidity and mortality, including heart failure (HF), coronary heart disease (CHD), and hypertension (HTN) (Hayes & colleagues, 2008).

To assess the connection between sleep hygiene, chronic illnesses, anxiety-related problems and insomnia among young adults attending college. The relationship between the dichotomized variables (insomnia and related complaints) and their predictors was examined using binary logistic regression. The results showed that increased SHI scores linked to insomnia symptoms (Javaheri & Redline, 2017). Sleep disturbance can result from almost any medical issue. Chronic insomnia sufferers are more likely to experience negative health consequences as a result of medical disease, and the prevalence of insomnia rises with age as medical issues become more prevalent (Spiegelhalder et al., 2010).

Rationale of Study

Chronic conditions including diabetes, heart disease, and cancer have significant psychological effects in addition to their physical health effects. Death anxiety, which results from a fear of dying and uncertainty about the course of the disease, is one of the most upsetting psychological experiences that people with these conditions go through. Significant emotional anguish brought on by death anxiety can have a detrimental effect on one's general well-being and mental health. Insomnia, a sleep problem marked by trouble falling or staying asleep, is one of the most prevalent effects of increased death fear. Patients with chronic illnesses who experience sleep disorders face greater physical and psychological strains, which results in worse disease management and a lower quality of life. However, not everyone reacts to death worry with the same degree of sleep disturbance, indicating that this association may be influenced by other psychological factors. The degree to which death dread contributes to insomnia may be determined in large part by coping mechanisms, which are the behavioral and cognitive measures people take to cope with stress.

Hypotheses of Study

1. There would be a significant positive relationship between death anxiety and insomnia among patients with chronic illness.
2. There would be a significant negative relationship between brief cope and insomnia among patients with chronic illness

3. Brief cope will mediate between death anxiety and insomnia among patients with chronic illness
4. There would be a significant mean difference of type of chronic illness on all study variables among patients of depression.

Research Methodology

Participants

The cross-sectional survey research approach served as the groundwork for this investigation. A sample of patients ($N= 250$) with chronic illness (cancer patient, heart patient and diabetic patient) will participate in this present study. Information was gathered from the Faisalabad division's hospitals. The technique of purposeful sampling was employed to gather data. Prior to distributing the surveys, the participants gave their informed consent.

Research Instruments

Informed Consent Form

Data confidentiality was ensured by assuring participants that their information would remain private. They gave a quick overview of the study's nature. Questionnaires and a relevant demographic sheet were attached. This information consist of, gender, age, type and duration of chronic illness.

Death Anxiety Scale

The Death Anxiety Scale constructed by Templer (1970). It consisting of 15 Items. The scale is based on negatively phrased items which are rated on a 5-point Likert scale which response pattern ranging from *Never* = 1 *Always* = 5. Individual can minimum obtain 15 scores on this scale whereas maximum scores cannot exceed than 75. Obtained scores on this scale were interpreted in terms of low and high score rather than cut of score. The reverse scoring items are 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, and 15. The scale has originally alpha reliability of .79.

Brief Cope

Brief cope Scale constructed by Carver (1997). It consisting of 28 items with three subscales, problem-focused coping have 8 items that are 2, 7, 10, 12, 14, 17, 23 and 25. Emotional focused coping have 12 items that are 5, 9, 13, 15, 18, 20, 21, 22, 24, 26, 27 and 28. Avoidant coping have 8 items that are 1, 3, 4, 6, 8, 11, 16 and 19. I haven't been doing this at all = 1 to I have been doing this a lot = 5 is the 4-point Likert-type response pattern used to rate the scale. This scale has no items with reverse scoring. The scale has originally alpha reliability of .72.

Insomnia Severity Index

Morin (1993) created the insomnia scale. There are seven things in it. Using a 5-point Likert scale with answer patterns ranging from *Never* = 0 to *Very Severe* = 4, the scale is based on negatively framed items. On this scale, a person can receive a minimum score of 0 and a maximum score of 28. The scores on this scale were interpreted as cut scores rather than low and high scores; scores ranging from 0 to 7 indicate no clinically significant insomnia, 8 to 14 indicate sub-threshold insomnia, 15 to 21 indicate moderately severe clinical insomnia, and 22 to 28 indicate severe clinical insomnia. No reverse scoring items in this scale. The scale has originally alpha reliability of .79

Procedure

Prior to collecting the data, consent from the relevant authorities will be sought. Following formal approval, the researcher personally approaches the participant, gives them a brief overview of the study, and encourages them to take part. The researcher guarantees that the findings will only be utilized for scholarly purposes and that the information will be kept private and never shared. Participants who demonstrated their willingness to participate in the study were encouraged to do so, and they were then asked to sign an informed permission form. They were given brief instructions to fill out the demographic sheet and complete the scales after providing signed informed consent. The researcher is present and attentive as the participants complete the scales, and if they encounter any challenges in comprehending the questions or completing the scales, the researcher responds to their inquiries in a suitable manner. Once participants have finished the scale, the researcher can verify the question to determine if it was left blank. If it was, the researcher asks the participants to fill in the appropriate area of the questionnaire. Due to their voluntary engagement in the study without receiving any material incentives, the participants received special gratitude from the researcher after completing the scales. The researcher values their participation and believes it adds significantly to our understanding of psychology.

Data Analysis

To examine the indirect effect of brief cope between death anxiety and insomnia, Mediation will be computed. Statistical analyses will be conducted including descriptive statistics, reliability analyses, skewness, Pearson correlation, independent sample t-test and ANOVA test

Results

Table 1

Demographic Information of the Participants

Demographic variables	F	%	M	SD
Gender				
Male	86	34.4	--	--
Female	164	65.6	--	--
Age				
Young adults	80	32	--	--
Middle adults	108	43.2	--	--
Late adults	62	24.8	--	--
Type of illness				
Cancer patient	97	38.8	--	--
Heart patient	97	38.8	--	--
Diabetic patient	56	22.4	--	--
Duration of illness				
1 to 3 year	94	37.6	--	--
4 to 6 year	124	49.6	--	--
7 and above	32	12.8	--	--
Death anxiety			45.22	17.47
PFC			11.53	5.03
EFC			12.67	3.96
AC			11.58	4.31
Insomnia			18.14	5.01

Note. $N = 250$

Table 1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of participants based on gender, age, type of illness, and duration of illness. Female ($f = 164, 65.6\%$) were greater in number as compare to male ($f = 86, 34.4\%$). Middle adults ($f = 108, 43.2\%$) participants were greater in number as compare to young adults ($f = 80, 32\%$) and late adults ($f = 62, 24.8\%$). Heart patients and cancer patients both ($f = 94, 38.8\%$) were greater in number as compare to diabetic patients ($f = 56, 22.4\%$). Participants with duration 4 to 6 years ($f = 124, 49.6\%$) were greater in numbers as compare to 1 to 3 years ($f = 94, 37.6\%$) and 7+ years ($f = 32, 12.8\%$). The mean and standard deviation of death anxiety ($M = 45.22, SD = 17.47$). It's indicated that a moderate level of death anxiety among the chronic ill patients. The mean and standard deviation of problem focused coping ($M = 11.53, SD = 5.03$). It's indicated that a moderate level of problem focused coping among the chronic ill patients. The mean and standard deviation of emotional focused coping ($M = 12.67, SD = 3.96$). It's indicated that a moderate level of emotional focused coping among the chronic ill patients. The mean and standard deviation of avoidant coping ($M = 11.58, SD = 4.31$). It's indicated that a moderate level of avoidant coping among the chronic ill patients. The mean and standard deviation of insomnia ($M = 18.14, SD = 5.01$). It's indicated that a moderate level of insomnia among the chronic ill patients.

Table 2

Reliability Analysis of Study Variables.

Variables	Items	α value
Death anxiety	15	.95
PFC	08	.70
EFC	12	.62
AC	08	.75
Insomnia	7	.81

Note. $N = 250$

The reliability analysis indicates that death anxiety .92, problem focused coping .70, emotional focused coping .62, avoidant coping .75 and insomnia .81 its consider good internal consistency.

Table 3

Pearson Correlation among study variables

Variables	M ± SD	1	2	3	4	5
Death anxiety	45.22± 17.47	1	-.78***	-.75***	-.63***	.55***
PFC	11.53±5.04		1	.88***	.74***	-.66***
EFC	12.67±3.96			1	.68***	-.78***
AC	11.58±4.31				1	-.39***
Insomnia	18.14±5.01					1

Note. N = 250

*** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$

The findings indicate that death anxiety have significant negative correlation with problem focused coping ($r = -.78, p < .001$), emotional focused coping ($r = -.75, p < .001$) and avoidant coping ($r = -.63, p < .001$) but significant positive with insomnia ($r = .55, p < .001$). The findings indicate that problem focused coping has significant positive correlation with emotional focused coping ($r = .88, p < .001$) and avoidant ($r = .74, p < .001$) but significant a negative with insomnia ($r = -.66, p < .001$). The findings indicate that emotional focused coping has a significant positive correlation with emotional avoidant coping ($r = .68, p < .001$) and significant negative relationship with insomnia ($r = -.78, p < .001$). The findings indicate that avoidant coping has significant negative relationship with insomnia ($r = -.39, p < .001$).

Table 4

Mediation analysis, using subscales of coping strategies as a mediators and insomnia as an outcome while death anxiety as a predictor chronic ill patient

Mediator	Path coefficients				(a*b)/c (95% CI)	R ²
	A	B	c	c ^{''}		
Problem focused Coping	-.224***	-.567***	.160***	.0333	.794 (.094, .159)	.442
Emotional focused Coping	-.171***	-1.057***	.160***	-.021	1.129 (.157, .202)	.617
Avoidant Coping	-.155***	***-.082	.160***	.147***	.079 (-.006, .037)	.316

Coping strategies as mediator, insomnia as an outcome and death anxiety as predictors among chronic ill patients. From the results we see that death anxiety was negatively associated with coping strategies like problem focused coping, emotional focused coping, and avoidant coping (from path a). The coping strategies like problem focused coping and emotional focused coping were significantly and negatively associated with insomnia while not significantly associated with avoidant coping (from path b). As for indirect effects, death anxiety was positively associated with insomnia (from path c). When coping strategies was involved in the model as a mediator, the direct pathway between death anxiety becomes in significant in problem focused and emotional focused coping that show fully mediate the relationship between death anxiety and insomnia.

Table 5

The comparison of Death Anxiety, Problem Focused Coping, Emotional Focused Coping, Avoidant Coping and Insomnia among Different Types of Chronic Ill Patients

Variables	SOV	Sum of squares	DF	Mean Square	F	P-value
Death Anxiety	Between Groups	28176.47	2	14.088	72.74	.000
	Within Groups	47838.85	247	193.67		
	Total	76014.33	249			
Problem focused Coping	Between Groups	2242.25	2	1121.12	67.87	.000
	Within Groups	4079.92	247	16.51		
	Total	6322.17	249			
Emotional focused Coping	Between Groups	1452.62	2	726.30	72.85	.000
	Within Groups	2462.48	247	9.97		
	Total	3915.10	249			

Avoidant coping	Between Groups	1934.66	2	967.33	88.55	.000
	Within Groups	2698.06	247			
	Total	4632.73	249			
Insomnia	Between Groups	1783.84	2	891.92	49.60	.000
	Within Groups	4441.52	247	17.98		
	Total	6225.37	249			

Note. $N = 250$

Table 5 shows mean, standard deviation and F -values for death anxiety, problem focused coping, emotional focused coping, avoidant coping and insomnia across chronic ill patients. Result indicted significant mean difference on all study variables which are death anxiety ($F=72.741$, $p=.000$), problem focused coping ($F=67.874$, $p=.000$), emotional focused coping ($F=72.853$, $p=.000$), avoidant coping ($F=88.557$, $p=.000$) and insomnia ($F=49.601$, $p=.000$).

Table 6

The Comparison of Death Anxiety, Problem Focused Coping, Emotional Focused Coping, Avoidant Coping and Insomnia among Different Duration of Chronic Ill Patients

Variables	SOV	Sum of squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Death Anxiety	Between Groups	1489.996	2	744.998	2.469	.087
	Within Groups	74524.340	247	301.718		
	Total	76014.3336	249			
Problem focused Coping	Between Groups	115.849	2	57.925	2.305	.102
	Within Groups	6206.327	247	25.127		
	Total	6322.176	249			
Emotional focused Coping	Between Groups	361.179	2	180.575	12.550	.000
	Within Groups	3553.955	247	14.388		
	Total	3915.104	249			
Avoidant coping	Between Groups	818.040	2	409.020	26.484	.000
	Within Groups	3814.696	247	15.444		
	Total	4632.736	249			
Insomnia	Between Groups	63.679	2	31.840	1.276	.281
	Within Groups	6161.697	247	24.946		
	Total	6166225.376	249			

Table 6 shows mean, standard deviation and F -values for death anxiety, problem focused coping, emotional focused coping, avoidant coping and insomnia across duration of chronic illness. Result indicted significant mean difference on emotional focused coping ($F=12.550$, $p=.000$) and avoidant coping ($F=26.484$, $p=.000$) but not non-significant on death anxiety ($F=67.874$, $p=.000$), problem focused coping ($F=2.469$, $p=.087$) and insomnia ($F=2.305$, $p=.281$).

Table 7

The Comparison of Death Anxiety, Problem Focused Coping, Emotional Focused Coping, Avoidant Coping and Insomnia among Different Age Groups of Chronic Ill Patients

Variables	SOV	Sum of squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Death Anxiety	Between Groups	21508.136	2	10754.068	48.733	.000
	Within Groups	54506.200	47	220.673	61.015	.000
	Total	76014.336	49			
Problem focused Coping	Between Groups	2090.600	2	1045.300	61.015	.000
	Within Groups	4231.576	47	17.132		
	Total	6322.176	49			
Emotional focused Coping	Between Groups	1177.557	2	588.778	53.124	.000
	Within Groups	2737.547	47	11.083		
	Total	3915.104	49			

Avoidant coping	Between Groups	1277.031	2	638.515	46.999	.000
	Within Groups	3355.705	47	13.586		
	Total	4632.736	49			
Insomnia	Between Groups	1032.508	2	516.254	24.556	.000
	Within Groups	5192.868	47	21.024		
	Total	6225.376	49			

Table 7 shows mean, standard deviation and F -values for death anxiety, problem focused coping, emotional focused coping, avoidant coping and insomnia across age groups of patients. Result indicted significant mean difference on all study variables death anxiety ($F=48.733$, $p=.000$), problem focused coping ($F=61.015$, $p=.000$), emotional focused coping ($F=53.124$, $p=.000$), avoidant coping ($F=46.999$, $p=.000$) and insomnia ($F=24.556$, $p=.000$).

Discussion

The current study focused on examining the effect of death anxiety on insomnia. And also examine the mediating effect of brief cope between them among chronic ill patients from Faisalabad division. Everyone feels sad or low sometimes, but these feelings usually pass with a little time. insomnia as a condition that affects sleep patterns, causing difficulties in falling or staying asleep, and outline its impact on physical and mental health. Insomnia and anxiety are closely linked, with anxiety often serving as a precursor to sleep disturbances. Chronic insomnia, exacerbated by anxiety, can have profound consequences on physical health, leading to an increased risk of cardiovascular disease, stroke, and other life-threatening conditions. The main objective of the study is to examine the direct and indirect effect of death anxiety on insomnia through brief cope among chronic ill patients. In order to achieve the objectives, three reliable and valid self-report questionnaires were administered to collect information about variable under study from patients including death anxiety scale by Morin (1992), Brief cope Scale by Carver (1997), and Insomnia Severity Index scale by Morin (1993). The major statistical analyses are Pearson correlation, regression, and mediation analysis, independent sample t-test and An ova were run to attain objective.

All hypotheses were supported in the present study. Results of this study show that significant correlations and associations were found in between variable. The hypothesis “There would be a significant positive relationship between death anxiety and insomnia among patients with chronic illness” was accepted in the present study. Literature also supported this. Results shows that the death anxiety have significant positive correlation with insomnia and results are consistent with a research study. Literature supported that hypothesis. A study conducted by (Menzies et al., 2024) results shows that there is significant positive relationship between death anxiety and insomnia. Some other research supports that the death anxiety has been found to relate to greater Insomnia. Impact of covid-19 pandemic on sleep disturbances due to fear of death (Çiftci et al., 2024; Bulut, & Kaygas, 2025).

Another study conducted by Glidewell (2023) results shows that death anxiety and insomnia have significant positive relationship and also present theoretical model. The findings of this study support the hypothesis that there is a significant positive relationship between death anxiety and insomnia. This suggests that individuals experiencing heightened death anxiety are more likely to suffer from insomnia, highlighting the potential importance of addressing both psychological and physiological aspects when treating this condition. New research suggests that death anxiety impacts sleep processes, as demonstrated by a positive association between death anxiety scores and nightmare occurrence, death representation in dreams, and repeated nightmares, as well as a correlation between death anxiety and men's procrastination before bed. A major components analysis indicates that dread of dying while sleeping is one of the primary causes of death anxiety. Even while similar circumstances may affect a broad spectrum people, individual responses may vary depending on the coping strategy selected (Folkman, 2012).

The hypothesis “There would be a significant negative relationship between brief cope and insomnia among patients with chronic illness” was accepted in the present study. Results shows that the brief cope (emotional focused, problem focused, avoidant coping) have significant negative effect relationship with insomnia and results are consistent with a research study. Literature supported that hypothesis. A study conducted by (Otsuka et al., 2021) results shows that self-concealment has significantly negative relation with insomnia. Another study

conducted by (Yamamoto et al., 2022) has showed that problem focused coping and insomnia have significant positive relationship.

Another study results show that avoidant coping initially improve the quality of sleep but not long time. The relationship between coping strategies and insomnia is significant, with problem-focused coping generally associated with better sleep outcomes, while avoidant coping tends to exacerbate sleep disturbances. Incorporating effective coping mechanisms, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), can lead to substantial improvements in sleep quality for individuals suffering from insomnia (Hürlimann et al., 2023).

Cancer patients frequently report difficulties falling and staying asleep due to fears of disease recurrence or death. Similarly, heart disease patients may experience nighttime panic and worry about sudden cardiac events, while diabetes patients often struggle with concerns about long term complications and mortality risk. Coping strategies refer to cognitive and behavioral efforts used to manage stress and emotional distress. Patients who engage in positive reframing, social support, mindfulness, and relaxation techniques tend to experience lower levels of distress. Patients who suppress their fears rather than addressing them may experience anxiety, rumination, and difficulty falling asleep (Margolis, 2018).

The hypothesis “Brief cope will mediate between death anxiety and insomnia among patients with chronic illness” was accepted in the present study. Results shows direct and indirect effect of death anxiety and insomnia. Present study confirmed through problem focused coping and emotional focused coping mediate the relation of death anxiety and insomnia but avoidant coping not mediate. Problem-focused coping strategies, which involve directly addressing stressors to alleviate anxiety, have been shown to influence sleep quality. A study found that higher use of problem-focused coping was associated with fewer depressive symptoms, leading to better subjective and objective sleep outcomes. Similarly, research involving breast cancer patients indicated that both emotion-focused and problem-focused coping strategies were linked to death anxiety through disease perception. This suggests that coping mechanisms can indirectly affect anxiety levels, which in turn may influence sleep quality (Kozusznik et al., 2021)

A study found that avoidance coping strategies mediated the relationship between stress and poor sleep quality, highlighting the role of coping mechanisms in sleep disturbances. While direct studies examining emotion-focused coping as a mediator between death anxiety and insomnia are limited, existing research suggests that emotion-focused coping can influence depressive symptoms, which in turn affect sleep quality. Further research is needed to directly investigate this mediating role. Patients who engage in positive reframing, social support, mindfulness, and relaxation techniques tend to experience lower levels of distress. A cancer patient practicing acceptance and finding meaning in their illness may experience reduced anxiety, leading to sleep to better sleep quality (Kim et al., 2022).

Conclusion

The current study was conducted to measure death anxiety as a predictor and insomnia as consequences among chronic patients and find out the mediating role of brief cope. Results suggested that high level of death anxiety leads toward the high level of sleeping disturbance (insomnia). Insomnia and anxiety are closely linked, with anxiety often serving as a precursor to sleep disturbances. Chronic insomnia, exacerbated by anxiety, can have profound consequences on physical health, leading to an increased risk of cardiovascular disease, stroke, and other life-threatening conditions. Addressing both anxiety and sleep disorders through early intervention and integrated treatment plans may help reduce the risk of these severe health outcomes and improve overall quality of life.

Recommendations

Future research should use a national sample in order to make broad conclusions. To increase the validity and applicability of the findings, future research should address these possible limitations and suggestions of this study.

References

- Abdel-Khalek, A. M. (2005). Death anxiety in clinical and non-clinical groups. *Death Studies*, 29(3), 251–259. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07481180590916371>
- Ahmad, N., Bibi, N., & Imran, M. (2023). *Effects of teacher's motivation on students' academic performance at public secondary schools in Karachi Pakistan*. American International Theism University Florida-USA (aituedu.org). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8141363>
- Al Maqbali, M. (2023). Impact of insomnia on mental status among chronic disease patients during COVID-19 pandemic. *Ethics, Medicine and Public Health*, 27, 100879. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemep.2023.100879>
- Ali, H., & Haq, A. U. (2017). Impact of privatization of banks on profitability. *Scientific Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 24-35.
- Ali, N., Bilal, M., Qureshi, S. A., Toru, N., & Rana, A. M. (2020). EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF PRIVATIZATION PROCESS IN PAKISTAN: EVIDENCE FROM STATISTICAL EXPERIENCE. *Sarhad Journal of Management Sciences*, 6(2), 385-402.
- Amjad, M., Akhtar, J., Anwar-ul-Haq, M., Yang, A., Akhtar, S. S., & Jacobsen, S.-E. (2014). Integrating role of ethylene and Aba in tomato plants adaptation to salt stress. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 172, 109–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2014.03.024>
- Assari, S., & Lankarani, M. M. (2016). Race and gender differences in correlates of death anxiety among elderly in the United States. *Iranian Journal of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences*, 10(2), e2024. <https://doi.org/10.17795/ijpbs-2024>
- Aurangzeb, D., & Haq, A. U. (2012). Factors affecting the trade balance in Pakistan. *Economics and Finance Review*, 1(11), 25-30.
- Azhar, Z. (2024). Blockchain as a Catalyst for Green and Digital HR Transformation: Strategies for Sustainable Workforce Management. *Open Access Library Journal*, 11(9), 1-22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1112060>
- Azhar, Z. (2024). The Role of Chatbots in Enhancing Job Seekers' and Employee Experience: A Case Study on CV Warehouse. *The Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 10(4), 23-35. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32861/jssr.10.4.23.35>
- Azhar, Z., & Imran, M. (2024). Ethical Considerations in the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management: A Comprehensive Review. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, 11(8).
- Azhar, Z., Nawaz, H., Malik, A. S., & Zaidi, M. H. (2022). Strategic Impact of Cloud Computing on HR Transformation. *International Journal of Social Science & Entrepreneurship*, 2(2), 546–576. <https://doi.org/10.58661/ijssse.v4i4.336>
- Baillette, P., & Barlette, Y. (2021). Coping strategies and paradoxes related to BYOD information security threats in France. *Research Anthology on Securing Mobile Technologies and Applications*, 527–558. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8545-0.ch03>
- Biggs, A., Brough, P., & Drummond, S. (2017). Lazarus and Folkman's psychological stress and coping theory. *The Handbook of Stress and Health*, 349–364. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118993811.ch21>
- Bulut, M. B., & Kaygas, Y. (2025). Does fear of death mediate the link between intolerance of uncertainty and sleep quality? Insights from earthquake survivors in containers. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 13591053251321774. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13591053251321774>
- Carver, C. S. (1997). You want to measure coping but your protocol's too long: Consider the Brief COPE. *International Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 4(1), 92–100. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327558ijbm0401_6
- Çiftci, N., Yildiz, M., & Uçar, M. (2024). Relationship between posttraumatic stress disorder, death anxiety, and insomnia in adults after the earthquake. *Omega: Journal of Death and Dying*, 00302228241256267. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00302228241256267>
- Danish, F., Akhtar, N., & Imran, M. (2025). AI-Driven Personalization in Educational Marketing: A Framework for Enhancing Student Recruitment and Retention. *Journal of Political Stability Archive*, 3(2), 559-590. <https://doi.org/10.63468/jpsa.3.2.33>
- Ferlay, J., Soerjomataram, I., Dikshit, R., Eser, S., Mathers, C., Rebelo, M., Parkin, D. M., Forman, D., & Bray, F. (2014). Cancer incidence and mortality worldwide: Sources, methods and major patterns in Globocan 2012. *International Journal of Cancer*, 136(5). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.29210>

- Folkman, S. (2013). Stress, coping, and hope. In *Psychological Aspects of Cancer* (pp. 119–127). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4866-2_8
- Forshaw, P. E., Correia, A. T. L., Roden, L. C., Lambert, E. V., & Rae, D. E. (2022). Sleep characteristics associated with nocturnal blood pressure nondipping in healthy individuals: a systematic review. *Blood Pressure Monitoring*, 27(6), 357–370. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MBP.0000000000000619>
- Ghulam, W. A., Ali, W., Ali, S., Khan, M. M., Khan, R. N. A., & Farooq, M. (2019). Investigating factors influencing Brain Drain of citizens of Azad Kashmir Pakistan. *The Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 53, 782–788. <https://doi.org/10.32861/jssr.53.782.788>
- Glidewell, R. N. (2023). Insomnia and death anxiety: A theoretical model with therapeutic implications. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*, 19(5), 1234-1242. <https://doi.org/10.5665/jcsm.10012>
- Hafeez, A., Yaseen, G., & Imran, M. (2019). Management Paradigm Change in Pak-Turk (International Schools & Colleges) After a Failed Military Coup in Turkey: A Case Study. <https://philpapers.org/rec/HAFMPC>
- Haq, E. U., & Khan, S. (2024). The Influence of Broken Homes on Students' Academic Performance in Schools. *Journal of Political Stability Archive*, 2(4), 339-361. <https://doi.org/10.63075/bnk5qv41>
- Hayes, D., Anstead, M. I., Ho, J., & Phillips, B. A. (2008). Insomnia and chronic heart failure. *Heart Failure Reviews*, 14(3), 171–182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10741-008-9102-1>
- Hürlimann, P., Bodenmann, G., Riemann, D., & Weitkamp, K. (2023). Cognitive behavioural therapy to treat stress and insomnia: A randomized wait list-controlled trial of two online courses. *Journal of Sleep Research*, 32(4), e13874. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsr.13874>
- Iqbal, T., Shah, S. M. A., & Abid, F. (2025). The Impact of Organizational Commitment and Supervisory Support on Employee Retention: Job Satisfaction as a Mediator in Pakistan's Pharmaceutical Sector. *Journal of Political Stability Archive*, 3(2), 287-305. <https://doi.org/10.63468/jpsa.3.2.16>
- Ivascu, L., Ali, W., Khalid, R., & Raza, M. (2022). The impact of competitive strategies on performance of banking sector; the mediating role of corporate social responsibility and operational excellence. *Energies*, 16(1), 297. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16010297>
- Jaleel, A., & Sarmad, M. (2024). Empowering leadership and the role of work-related curiosity in employee job crafting behavior: the role of low gender egalitarianism. *The Learning Organization*, 31(6), 1008-1030. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TLO-08-2023-0148>
- Jaleel, A., Rabbani, S., & Sarmad, M. (2025). Unlocking the effects of joyous exploration and deprivation sensitivity on employees' job crafting behavior: a moderating and mediating mechanism. *Career Development International*, 30(3), 326-344. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/CDI-11-2023-0412>
- Jalil, A., Sarmad, M., & Shafi, M. Q. (2023). Abusive supervision fosters employees' silence: the mediating role of avoidance orientation and moderating role of leader-member exchange. *International Journal of Business and Systems Research*, 17(3), 291-308. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/IJBSR.2022.10045213>
- Khan, S., & Haq, E. U. (2025). The Role of Pedagogical Strategies in Teaching Management Science to Hospitality Management Students. *Journal of Political Stability Archive*, 3(1), 805-826. <https://doi.org/10.63468/jpsa.3.1.48>
- Khan, S., Haq, A. U., & Naseer, M. (2022). The Influence of Guerrilla Marketing on Consumer Buying Behavior in the Beverage Sector of Rawalpindi and Islamabad, Pakistan. *Journal of Development and Social Sciences*, 3(4), 647-659. [https://doi.org/10.47205/jdss.2022\(3-IV\)60](https://doi.org/10.47205/jdss.2022(3-IV)60)
- Khan, U. S. D. Z. U., & Khan, S. (2020). Impact of Employees' Behavior on Sales: A Case Study of L'oreal Pakistan. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review*, 4(1), 907-917. <https://pssr.org.pk/issues/v4/1/impact-of-employees-behavior-on-sales-a-case-study-of-loreal-pakistan.pdf>
- Khoso, F. J., Shaikh, N., Dahri, K. H., & Imran, M. (2024). Educational Nurturing in Underdeveloped Contexts Unraveling the Dynamics of Student Teachers' Holistic Development. *Spry Contemporary Educational Practices*, 3(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.62681/sprypublishers.scep/3/1/3>
- Lehto, R. H., & Stein, K. F. (2009). Death anxiety: An analysis of an evolving concept. *Research and Theory for Nursing Practice*, 23(1), 23–41. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1541-6577.23.1.23>
- Malik, A., Hanif, H., & Elahi, M. (2025). Impact of Diversification, Political Stability & Regulatory Quality on Financial Performance: Empirical Evidence from Banking Sector of Pakistan. *Journal of Political Stability Archive*, 3(1), 602-626. <http://dx.doi.org/10.63468/jpsa.3.1.37>

- Mankash, M. A., Ahmed, S. T., Shabbir, N., & Imran, M. (2025). Second Language Learning in the Digital Age: How Technology Shapes Language Acquisition at Universities in Karachi, Pakistan. *Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review*, 3(1), 182-199. <https://llrjournal.com/index.php/11/article/view/83>
- Margolis, E. (2018). *The Impact of Emotion Regulation, Anxiety, and Sleep Disturbance on Coping among HIV-Positive Adults*. Palo Alto University.
- Muhammad, S., Afridi, F. K., Ali, M. W., Shah, W. U., & Alasan, I. I. (2020). Effect of training on employee commitment: mediating role of job satisfaction. *Pakistan Journal of Society, Education and Language (PJSEL)*, 7(1), 28-37. <https://jehanf.com/pjsel/index.php/journal/article/view/299>
- Naseer, M., Haq, A. U., & Shah, S. M. A. (2024). Understanding Turnover Intentions in Pakistan's Healthcare Sector: A Qualitative Exploration of Supervisory Behavior, Stress, and Cultural Norms. *Annual Methodological Archive Research Review*, 2(5), 1-18.
- Naseer, M., Khan, S., Khan, R., & Minhas, A. A. (2021). Employee Retention and Job Satisfaction in the Era of Transformative Marketing: An Investigation in Context of Pakistan. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 12(2), 640-653. <http://dx.doi.org/10.34218/IJM.12.2.2021.063>
- Naseer, M., Rehan, M. S., & Shah, S. M. A. (2024). Exploring the Determinants of Career Satisfaction Among Employees: Evidence from Pakistan's Pharmaceutical Sector. *Journal of Political Stability Archive*, 2(4), 207-225. <https://journalpsa.com.pk/index.php/JPSA/article/view/44>
- Pandya, A., & Kathuria, T. (2021). Death anxiety, religiosity and culture: Implications for therapeutic process and future research. *Religions*, 12(1), 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12010061>
- Perveen, F., Aksar, M., Ul Haq, A., & Hassan, S. (2020). Variance decomposition in dividend policy at three levels. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences (IJMESS)*, 9(1), 24-36. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32327/IJMESS/9.1.2020.2>
- Peters, S. A., Huxley, R. R., & Woodward, M. (2014). Diabetes as a risk factor for stroke in women compared with men: A systematic review and meta-analysis of 64 cohorts, including 775 385 individuals and 12 539 strokes. *The Lancet*, 383(9933), 1973–1980. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(14\)60040-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(14)60040-4)
- Rana, A. M., Zainol, F. A., Yaacob, M. R., Ahmad, H., & Rehman, K.-U.-. (2018). Organizational commitment and ethical conduct on team performance: Evidence from Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(7). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v8-i7/4344>
- Regier, D. A., Kuhl, E. A., & Kupfer, D. J. (2013). The DSM-5: Classification and criteria changes. *World Psychiatry*, 12(2), 92–98. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20050>
- Riemann, D., Spiegelhalder, K., Feige, B., Voderholzer, U., Berger, M., Perlis, M., & Nissen, C. (2010). The hyperarousal model of insomnia: A review of the concept and its evidence. *Sleep Medicine Reviews*, 14(1), 19–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smrv.2009.04.002>
- Rösler, L., van Kesteren, E.-J., Leerssen, J., van der Lande, G., Lakbila-Kamal, O., Foster-Dingley, J. C., Albers, A., & van Someren, E. J. W. (2024). Hyperarousal dynamics reveal an overnight increase boosted by insomnia. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 179, 279–285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2024.09.032>
- Shah, S. M. A., Qazi, A. H., & Khan, A. R. (2025). Exploring Synergies: Hr, Finance, And Sustainable Supply Chains. *Qualitative Research Review Letter*, 3(1), 218-254. <https://doi.org/10.63075/yfbnv137>
- Shah, S., Khan, M., Haq, A. U., & Hayat, M. . (2023). COVID-19 Precautions of Pakistani Banks in the Lens of Qualitative Study Approach. *Global Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 2(2), 16–30. <https://doi.org/10.59129/gjhssr.v2.i2.2023.15>
- Shaukat, U., Qureshi, S. A., & Ul Haq, A. (2020). Derivative Usage and Bank Stability: A Comparison of Islamic and Conventional Banking from Pakistan. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review*, 4(1), 943-954. [http://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2020\(4-1\)72](http://doi.org/10.35484/pssr.2020(4-1)72)
- Shaukat, U., Rehman, A., & ul Haq, A. (2021). Pairs Trading and Stock Returns: An Evidence from Pakistan Stock Exchange. *City University Research Journal*, 11(2). <https://cusitjournals.com/index.php/CURJ/article/view/501>
- Sohail-Rehan, M., & Ul-Haq, A. (2018). The impact of multiple types of crises on human resource management among export oriented textile industry of Pakistan. *Recent Issues in Human Resource Management*, 1(1), 54-56.
- Spiegelhalder, K. (2010). The association between insomnia and cardiovascular diseases. *Nature and Science of Sleep*, 71. <https://doi.org/10.2147/nss.s7471>

- Sultana, Z., & Imran, M. (2024). Challenges Faced by English Teachers in Pakistan. *Spry Journal of Literature and Linguistics*, 2(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.62681/sprypublishers.sjll/2/1/1>
- ul Haq, A. (2017). Firm characteristics and cash-cash flow sensitivity of the manufacturing sector of Pakistan. *Business & Economic Review*, 9(3), 71–103. <https://doi.org/10.22547/ber/9.3.3>
- ul Haq, A., & ur Rehman, K. (2017). Major Challenges and Opportunities for Islamic Banking and SMEs in Pakistan. *Journal of Managerial Sciences*, XI(3), 355-370.
- ul Haq, A., Niazi, G. S. K., & Sahto, Q. (2012). Some New Evidence on Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment: A Case Study of Pakistan. *Actual Problems of Economics*, 2(4), 76-82
- Wolińska, W., Brzeźniak, H., & Mroczek, B. (2020). Analysis of the relationship between insomnia and adult chronic diseases with regard to working conditions. *Family Medicine & Primary Care Review*, 22(3), 228–234. <https://doi.org/10.5114/fmPCR.2020.98251>
- Yamamoto, N., Aihara, Y., Yasuoka, M., & Maeda, M. (2022). The relationship between coping strategies and insomnia in Japanese workers: A cross-sectional study. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 18, 135–144. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NDT.S347682>